

Electronic Companion - Blockchain-enabled Local Market for Sharing Storage in Energy Communities

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Abstract—This electronic companion is part of the manuscript entitled “Blockchain-enabled local markets for sharing storage in energy communities” which has been exclusively submitted to the IEEE Innovative Smart Grid Technologies (ISGT) – Middle East 2023 conference. It comprises the complete mathematical formulation for all market participants, the collection of Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions for all models and the proofs for the equivalence of Equilibrium Model and Optimization Model. We show this way that market is efficient; the system is dispatched at the minimum social cost and no one is motivated to deviate from the market clearing outcomes. We also prove market’s revenue adequacy, which implies that the market operator never incurs a budget deficit. Finally, we provide some technical parameters and data used in the case studies.

I. MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

The mathematical formulation of the two local market models is presented in this section. Note that dual variables are listed alongside each constraint.

A. Multi-Player External Storage Equilibrium Model (Equil-MPES)

In *Equil-MPES*, comprising (1a)-(1g), nine sets of optimization problems (one per market participant) and the set of sharing constraints are provided. First, we present the optimization problems of the players who are not ES owners and thereby are potential PSR buyers, starting from the arbitrageur $i \in \hat{A}$:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Maximize}_{\hat{\Xi}_{\hat{A}}} \sum_{t,s} \left[\frac{\lambda_t^{\text{loc}}}{\Delta T/h} (p_{i,s,t}^d - p_{i,s,t}^c) - p_{i,s,t}^{c,\max} \mu_{s,t}^c \right. \\ \left. - p_{i,s,t}^{d,\max} \mu_{s,t}^d - e_{i,s,t}^{\max} \mu_{s,t}^e \right] + \sum_s \tilde{\lambda} e_{i,s,T} \end{array} \right. \quad (1\text{aa})$$

subject to:

$$0 \leq p_{i,s,t}^c \leq p_{i,s,t}^{c,\max} : \theta_{i,s,t}^c, \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^c \quad \forall t, s \quad (1\text{ab})$$

$$0 \leq p_{i,s,t}^d \leq p_{i,s,t}^{d,\max} : \theta_{i,s,t}^d, \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^d \quad \forall t, s \quad (1\text{ac})$$

$$0 \leq e_{i,s,t} \leq e_{i,s,t}^{\max} : \underline{\theta}_{i,s,t}^e, \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^e \quad \forall t, s \quad (1\text{ad})$$

$$e_{i,s,t} = E_{i,s}^{\text{ini}} + p_{i,s,t}^c \eta_s^c - \frac{p_{i,s,t}^d}{\eta_s^d} : \gamma_{i,s,t}^e \quad \forall s, t = 1 \quad (1\text{ae})$$

$$e_{i,s,t} = e_{i,s,t-1} + p_{i,s,t}^c \eta_s^c - \frac{p_{i,s,t}^d}{\eta_s^d} : \gamma_{i,s,t}^e \quad \forall s, t > 1 \quad (1\text{af})$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \\ \\ \\ \end{array} \right\} \forall i \in \hat{A}$$

where $\hat{\Xi}_{\hat{A}} = \left\{ p_{i,s,t}^c, p_{i,s,t}^d, e_{i,s,t}, p_{i,s,t}^{c,\max}, p_{i,s,t}^{d,\max}, e_{i,s,t}^{\max} \right\}$ is the set of primal variables. Objective function (1aa) maximizes the profit of the arbitrageur. More specifically, it buys charge right $p_{i,s,t}^{c,\max}$, discharge right $p_{i,s,t}^{d,\max}$ and capacity rights $e_{i,s,t}^{\max}$ at time t from storage s (storage owner s) at prices $\mu_{s,t}^c$, $\mu_{s,t}^d$ and $\mu_{s,t}^e$, respectively. Note that these prices are market outcomes (variables for the equilibrium), while parameters within (1a). Subsequently, according to the total PSR obtained, the arbitrageur charges power $p_{i,s,t}^c$ or discharges power $p_{i,s,t}^d$ at local market price λ_t^{loc} . The local price λ_t^{loc} , like the PSR prices, is a variable for the equilibrium, while parameter for (1a). Constraints (1ae)-(1af) calculate the SOC ($e_{i,s,t}$) of the ES. Parameter $E_{i,s}^{\text{ini}}$ expresses the initial state-of-charge (SOC) and η_s^c, η_s^d are the (dis)charge efficiencies for storage s . The term $\Delta T/h$ expresses the number of time intervals in one hour. Parameter $\tilde{\lambda}$ is the so-called energy value and reflects the value of each kWh of the residual energy in ES at the end of the time horizon considered, i.e., $t = T$. Constraints (1ab)-(1ad) impose that the actual storage (dis)charge power and the SOC are non-negative and bounded by the corresponding PSR variables.

Likewise, the profit-maximization problem for each renewable producer $i \in \hat{P}$ is given by (1b) below. This RES producer does not own any ES, but it is willing to buy PSRs:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Maximize}_{\hat{\Xi}_{\hat{P}}} \sum_t \left[\frac{\lambda_t^{\text{loc}}}{\Delta T/h} p_{i,t}^g + \sum_s \left(\frac{\lambda_t^{\text{loc}}}{\Delta T/h} p_{i,s,t}^d \right. \right. \end{array} \right.$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} & - p_{i,s,t}^{c,\max} \mu_{s,t}^c - p_{i,s,t}^{d,\max} \mu_{s,t}^d - e_{i,s,t}^{\max} \mu_{s,t}^e \Big) \Big] \\ & + \sum_s \tilde{\lambda} e_{i,s,T} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1ba)$$

subject to:

$$(1ab) - (1ad) \forall t; (1ae) t = 1; (1af) t > 1, \forall s \quad (1bb)$$

$$0 \leq p_{i,t}^g : \theta_{i,t}^g; 0 \leq p_{i,t}^l : \theta_{i,t}^l, \forall t \quad (1bc)$$

$$p_{i,t}^g = G_{i,t}^{\text{RES}} - \sum_s p_{i,s,t}^c - p_{i,t}^l : \gamma_{i,t}^g \forall t \Big\} \forall i \in \hat{\mathcal{P}} \quad (1bd)$$

where $\hat{\Xi}_{\hat{\mathcal{P}}} = \{p_{i,s,t}^c, p_{i,s,t}^d, e_{i,s,t}, p_{i,s,t}^{c,\max}, p_{i,s,t}^{d,\max}, e_{i,s,t}^{\max}, p_{i,t}^g, p_{i,t}^l\}$ is the set of primal variables. Constraint (1bd) implies that the produced renewable power ($G_{i,t}^{\text{RES}}$) can either directly be sold to the grid ($p_{p,t}^g$), curtailed ($p_{p,t}^l$), or stored in the ES ($p_{i,s,t}^c$) whose rights are being bought.

Furthermore, the cost-minimization problem for each consumer $i \in \hat{\mathcal{C}}$ is given by (1c). Similarly, no ES belongs to this consumer, but it bids to buy PSRs from the storage owners:

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} & \text{Minimize} \sum_t \left[-\frac{\lambda_t^{\text{loc}}}{\Delta T/h} q_{i,t} + \frac{V_i}{\Delta T/h} p_{i,t}^{\text{shed}} \right. \\ & + \sum_s \left(p_{i,s,t}^{c,\max} \mu_{s,t}^c + p_{i,s,t}^{d,\max} \mu_{s,t}^d + e_{i,s,t}^{\max} \mu_{s,t}^e \right) \\ & \left. - \sum_s \tilde{\lambda} e_{i,s,T} \right] \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1ca)$$

subject to:

$$(1ab) - (1ad) \forall t; (1ae) t = 1; (1af) t > 1, \forall s \quad (1cb)$$

$$0 \leq p_{i,t}^{\text{shed}} \leq D_{i,t} : \underline{\delta}_{i,t}, \bar{\delta}_{i,t} \forall t \quad (1cc)$$

$$q_{i,t} = \sum_s (p_{i,s,t}^d - p_{i,s,t}^c) - D_{i,t} + p_{i,t}^{\text{shed}} : \gamma_{i,t}^q \forall t \quad (1cd)$$

$$\Big\} \forall i \in \hat{\mathcal{C}}$$

where $\hat{\Xi}_{\hat{\mathcal{C}}} = \{p_{i,s,t}^c, p_{i,s,t}^d, e_{i,s,t}, p_{i,s,t}^{c,\max}, p_{i,s,t}^{d,\max}, e_{i,s,t}^{\max}, q_{i,t}, p_{i,t}^{\text{shed}}\}$ is the set of primal variables. Constraint (1cc) binds the total shedding power ($p_{i,t}^{\text{shed}}$) to be non-negative and less than or equal to the total load ($D_{i,t}$). Constraint (1cd) defines the consumer's net energy generation ($q_{i,t}$) (if positive) and consumption (if negative). Parameter V_i declares the value of lost load.

In addition, the cost-minimization problem of each prosumer $i \in \hat{\mathcal{R}}$ who has no ES is given by (1d) below:

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} & \text{Minimize (1ca)} \\ & \hat{\Xi}_{\hat{\mathcal{R}}} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1da)$$

subject to:

$$(1ab) - (1ad) \forall t; (1ae) t = 1; (1af) t > 1, \forall s \quad (1db)$$

$$(1cc) \forall t \quad (1dc)$$

$$0 \leq p_{i,t}^{\text{PV}} \leq G_{i,t}^{\text{PV}} : \underline{\rho}_{i,t}, \bar{\rho}_{i,t} \forall t \quad (1dd)$$

$$q_{i,t} = \sum_s (p_{i,s,t}^d - p_{i,s,t}^c) - D_{i,t} + p_{i,t}^{\text{shed}} + p_{i,t}^{\text{PV}}$$

$$: \gamma_{i,t}^q \forall t \Big\} \forall i \in \hat{\mathcal{R}} \quad (1de)$$

where $\hat{\Xi}_{\hat{\mathcal{R}}} = \{p_{i,s,t}^c, p_{i,s,t}^d, e_{i,s,t}, p_{i,s,t}^{c,\max}, p_{i,s,t}^{d,\max}, e_{i,s,t}^{\max}, q_{i,t}, p_{i,t}^{\text{shed}}, p_{i,t}^{\text{PV}}\}$ is the set of primal variables. Variable $p_{i,t}^{\text{PV}}$ expresses the utilized PV power, while $G_{i,t}^{\text{PV}}$ is the total PV production.

Lastly, the profit-maximization problem for the grid owner is given by (1e) below:

$$\text{Maximize} \sum_t p_t^{\text{flow}} (\lambda_t^{\text{DA}} - \lambda_t^{\text{loc}}) \quad (1ea)$$

subject to:

$$-L \leq p_t^{\text{flow}} \leq L : \underline{\beta}_t, \bar{\beta}_t \forall t \quad (1eb)$$

where parameter L is the capacity of the grid (equivalent to a single line) to connect the local market to the distribution system, and p_t^{flow} is the flow across that line (positive if the local market transfers power to the distribution system, negative if otherwise). Objective function (1ea) maximizes the profit of the grid owner. It performs spatial arbitrage between the DA distribution-level market and the local market at prices λ_t^{DA} and λ_t^{loc} , respectively. These two prices are expected to be different when the line is congested.

The profit-maximization problem for the external storage supplier is given by (1f) below:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Maximize} \sum_{s,t} \left[p_{s,t}^{c,\text{ri}} (\mu_{s,t}^c - W_s^c) + p_{s,t}^{d,\text{ri}} (\mu_{s,t}^d - W_s^d) \right. \\ & \left. + e_{s,t}^{\text{ri}} (\mu_{s,t}^e - W_s^e) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (1fa)$$

subject to:

$$0 \leq p_{s,t}^{c,\text{ri}} \leq P_s^{c,\max} : \underline{\phi}_{s,t}^c, \bar{\phi}_{s,t}^c \forall t, s \quad (1fb)$$

$$0 \leq p_{s,t}^{d,\text{ri}} \leq P_s^{d,\max} : \underline{\phi}_{s,t}^d, \bar{\phi}_{s,t}^d \forall t, s \quad (1fc)$$

$$0 \leq e_{s,t}^{\text{ri}} \leq E_s^{\max} : \underline{\phi}_{s,t}^e, \bar{\phi}_{s,t}^e \forall t, s. \quad (1fd)$$

Finally, the shared linking constraints related to PSRs, as well as the power balance constraint are given by (1g) below:

$$p_{s,t}^{c,\text{ri}} = \sum_{i \in (\hat{\mathcal{A}} \cup \hat{\mathcal{P}} \cup \hat{\mathcal{C}} \cup \hat{\mathcal{R}})} p_{i,s,t}^{c,\max} : \mu_{s,t}^c \forall s, t \quad (1ga)$$

$$p_{s,t}^{d,\text{ri}} = \sum_{i \in (\hat{\mathcal{A}} \cup \hat{\mathcal{P}} \cup \hat{\mathcal{C}} \cup \hat{\mathcal{R}})} p_{i,s,t}^{d,\max} : \mu_{s,t}^d \forall s, t \quad (1gb)$$

$$e_{s,t}^{\text{ri}} = \sum_{i \in (\hat{\mathcal{A}} \cup \hat{\mathcal{P}} \cup \hat{\mathcal{C}} \cup \hat{\mathcal{R}})} e_{i,s,t}^{\max} : \mu_{s,t}^e \forall s, t \quad (1gc)$$

$$\begin{aligned} p_t^{\text{flow}} &= \sum_{i \in \hat{\mathcal{A}}, s} (p_{i,s,t}^d - p_{i,s,t}^c) + \sum_{i \in \hat{\mathcal{P}}} \left(p_{i,t}^g + \sum_s p_{i,s,t}^d \right) \\ &+ \sum_{i \in (\hat{\mathcal{C}} \cup \hat{\mathcal{R}})} q_{i,t} : \lambda_t^{\text{loc}} \forall t. \end{aligned} \quad (1gd)$$

Constraints (1ga) - (1gc), that correspond to charge, discharge and capacity rights respectively, imply that for each storage

and in each hour, the total purchased PSRs by all the players should be equal to the total sold ones. Constraint (1gd) enforces the power balance. Note that the dual variables of (1g) provide the PSR and the local energy prices.

B. Multi-Player External Storage Optimization Model (Opt-MPES)

Opt-MPES is a linear optimization model in which the objective is to minimize the local system cost. The model is given by (2) below:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Minimize}_{\Xi_{\text{Opt-MPES}}} \sum_t \left[-\lambda_t^{\text{DA}} p_t^{\text{flow}} + \sum_{i \in (\hat{\mathcal{C}} \cup \hat{\mathcal{R}})} V_i p_{i,t}^{\text{shed}} + \right. \\ \left. \sum_s \left(W_s^c p_{s,t}^{c,\text{ri}} + W_s^d p_{s,t}^{d,\text{ri}} + W_s^e e_{s,t}^{\text{ri}} \right) \right] - \sum_{i \in \hat{\mathcal{I}},s} \tilde{\lambda} e_{i,s,T} \end{aligned} \quad (2a)$$

subject to:

$$(1ab) - (1af); (1bb) - (1bd); (1cb) - (1cd); (1db) - (1de);$$

$$(1fb) - (1fd); (1eb); (1ga) - (1gd) \quad (2b)$$

The set of decision variables of problem (2a), i.e., $\Xi_{\text{Opt-MPES}}$, includes all variables stated in problems (1a)-(1d), (1e) and (1f) of *Equil-MPES*. Furthermore, the set of constraints stated in (2b), contains identical constraints to the ones considered by the players in *Equil-MPES*, as well as the same shared linking constraints.

II. KKTs FOR ALL MODELS

A. KKTs of Model *Equil-MPES*

The KKT optimality conditions associated with model *Equil-MPES* are given by (3) below. Note that \mathcal{L} is the Lagrangian function with respect to each player's problem. Firstly, we provide the KKTs for the players bidding for to obtain physical storage rights. Afterwards, the optimality conditions for the grid owner are presented.

$$\left\{ (1ae), (1af) \right. \quad (3aa)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial p_{i,s,t}^c} = \lambda_t^{\text{loc}} - \underline{\theta}_{i,s,t}^c + \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^c + \gamma_{i,s,t}^e \eta_s^c = 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (3ab)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial p_{i,s,t}^d} = -\lambda_t^{\text{loc}} - \underline{\theta}_{i,s,t}^d + \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^d - \frac{\gamma_{i,s,t}^e}{\eta_s^d} = 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (3ac)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial e_{i,s,t}} = -\underline{\theta}_{i,s,t}^e + \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^e - \gamma_{i,s,t}^e + \gamma_{i,s,t+1}^e = 0 \quad \forall s, t \leq 23 \quad (3ad)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial e_{i,s,t}} = -\underline{\theta}_{i,s,t}^e + \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^e - \gamma_{i,s,t}^e - \tilde{\lambda} = 0 \quad \forall s, t = 24 \quad (3ae)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial p_{i,s,t}^{c,\text{max}}} = -\bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^c + \mu_{s,t}^c = 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (3af)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial p_{i,s,t}^{d,\text{max}}} = -\bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^d + \mu_{s,t}^d = 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (3ag)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial e_{i,s,t}^{\text{max}}} = -\bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^e + \mu_{s,t}^e = 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (3ah)$$

$$0 \leq p_{i,s,t}^c \perp \underline{\theta}_{i,s,t}^c \geq 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (3ai)$$

$$0 \leq p_{i,s,t}^d \perp \underline{\theta}_{i,s,t}^d \geq 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (3aj)$$

$$0 \leq e_{i,s,t} \perp \underline{\theta}_{i,s,t}^e \geq 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (3ak)$$

$$0 \leq (p_{i,s,t}^{c,\text{max}} - p_{i,s,t}^c) \perp \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^c \geq 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (3al)$$

$$0 \leq (p_{i,s,t}^{d,\text{max}} - p_{i,s,t}^d) \perp \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^d \geq 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (3am)$$

$$0 \leq (e_{i,s,t}^{\text{max}} - e_{i,s,t}) \perp \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^e \geq 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad \left. \right\} \quad \forall i \in \hat{\mathcal{A}}. \quad (3an)$$

$$\left\{ (1ae), (1af), (1bd) \right. \quad (3ba)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial p_{i,s,t}^c} = -\underline{\theta}_{i,s,t}^c + \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^c + \gamma_{i,s,t}^e \eta_s^c + \gamma_{i,t}^g = 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (3bb)$$

$$(3ac) - (3an) \quad (3bc)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial p_{i,t}^g} = -\lambda_t^{\text{loc}} - \theta_{i,t}^g + \gamma_{i,t}^g = 0 \quad \forall t \quad (3bd)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial p_{i,t}^l} = -\theta_{i,t}^l + \gamma_{i,t}^g = 0 \quad \forall t \quad (3be)$$

$$0 \leq p_{i,t}^g \perp \theta_{i,t}^g \geq 0 \quad \forall t \quad (3bf)$$

$$0 \leq p_{i,t}^l \perp \theta_{i,t}^l \geq 0 \quad \forall t \quad \left. \right\} \quad \forall i \in \hat{\mathcal{P}}. \quad (3bg)$$

$$\left\{ (1ae), (1af), (1cd) \right. \quad (3ca)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial p_{i,s,t}^c} = -\underline{\theta}_{i,s,t}^c + \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^c + \gamma_{i,s,t}^e \eta_s^c + \gamma_{i,t}^g = 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (3cb)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial p_{i,s,t}^d} = \underline{\theta}_{i,s,t}^d + \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^d - \frac{\gamma_{i,s,t}^e}{\eta_s^d} - \gamma_{i,t}^g = 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (3cc)$$

$$(3ad) - (3an) \quad (3cd)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial q_{i,t}} = -\lambda_t^{\text{loc}} + \gamma_{i,t}^g = 0 \quad \forall t \quad (3ce)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial p_{i,t}^{\text{shed}}} = V_c - \underline{\delta}_{i,t} + \bar{\delta}_{i,t} - \gamma_{i,t}^g = 0 \quad \forall t \quad (3cf)$$

$$0 \leq p_{i,t}^{\text{shed}} \perp \underline{\delta}_{i,t} \geq 0 \quad \forall t \quad (3cg)$$

$$0 \leq (D_{i,t} - p_{i,t}^{\text{shed}}) \perp \bar{\delta}_{i,t} \geq 0 \quad \forall t \quad \left. \right\} \quad \forall i \in \hat{\mathcal{C}}. \quad (3ch)$$

$$\left\{ (1ae), (1af), (1de) \right. \quad (3da)$$

$$(3cb) - (3ch) \quad (3db)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial p_{i,t}^{\text{PV}}} = -\underline{\rho}_{i,t} + \bar{\rho}_{i,t} - \gamma_{i,t}^g = 0 \quad \forall t \quad (3dc)$$

$$0 \leq p_{i,t}^{\text{PV}} \perp \underline{\rho}_{i,t} \geq 0 \quad \forall t \quad (3dd)$$

$$0 \leq (G_{i,t}^{\text{PV}} - p_{i,t}^{\text{PV}}) \perp \bar{\rho}_{i,t} \geq 0 \quad \forall t \quad \left. \right\} \quad \forall i \in \hat{\mathcal{R}}. \quad (3de)$$

The optimality conditions for the grid owner are given by (3e) below:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial p_t^{\text{flow}}} = \lambda_t^{\text{loc}} - \lambda_t^{\text{DA}} - \underline{\beta}_t + \bar{\beta}_t = 0 \quad \forall t \quad (3ea)$$

$$0 \leq (L + p_t^{\text{flow}}) \perp \underline{\beta}_t \geq 0 \quad \forall t \quad (3eb)$$

$$0 \leq (L - p_t^{\text{flow}}) \perp \bar{\beta}_t \geq 0 \quad \forall t. \quad (3ec)$$

The shared constraints which express the provision of the physical storage rights as well as the power balance are expressed by (1ga) - (1gd).

B. KKTs of Model Opt-MPES

It is straightforward to verify that the KKT optimality conditions of *Opt-MPES* are identical to those of *Equil-MPES*. To avoid replicating the equations, we will only provide an example selecting a random player and derive its KKTs, i.e., the arbitrageur $i \in \hat{\mathcal{A}}$.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (1ae), (1af) \end{array} \right. \quad (4aa)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial p_{i,s,t}^c} = \lambda_t^{\text{loc}} - \underline{\theta}_{i,s,t}^c + \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^c + \gamma_{i,s,t}^e \eta_s^c = 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (4ab)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial p_{i,s,t}^d} = -\lambda_t^{\text{loc}} - \underline{\theta}_{i,s,t}^d + \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^d - \frac{\gamma_{i,s,t}^e}{\eta_s^d} = 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (4ac)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial e_{i,s,t}} = -\underline{\theta}_{i,s,t}^e + \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^e - \gamma_{i,s,t}^e + \gamma_{i,s,t+1}^e = 0 \quad \forall s, t \leq 23 \quad (4ad)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial e_{i,s,t}} = -\underline{\theta}_{i,s,t}^e + \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^e - \gamma_{i,s,t}^e - \tilde{\lambda} = 0 \quad \forall s, t = 24 \quad (4ae)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial p_{i,s,t}^{c,\max}} = -\bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^c + \mu_{s,t}^c = 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (4af)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial p_{i,s,t}^{d,\max}} = -\bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^d + \mu_{s,t}^d = 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (4ag)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial e_{i,s,t}^{\max}} = -\bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^e + \mu_{s,t}^e = 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (4ah)$$

$$0 \leq p_{i,s,t}^c \perp \underline{\theta}_{i,s,t}^c \geq 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (4ai)$$

$$0 \leq p_{i,s,t}^d \perp \underline{\theta}_{i,s,t}^d \geq 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (4aj)$$

$$0 \leq e_{i,s,t} \perp \underline{\theta}_{i,s,t}^e \geq 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (4ak)$$

$$0 \leq (p_{i,s,t}^{c,\max} - p_{i,s,t}^c) \perp \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^c \geq 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (4al)$$

$$0 \leq (p_{i,s,t}^{d,\max} - p_{i,s,t}^d) \perp \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^d \geq 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad (4am)$$

$$0 \leq (e_{i,s,t}^{\max} - e_{i,s,t}) \perp \bar{\theta}_{i,s,t}^e \geq 0 \quad \forall t, s \quad \forall i \in \hat{\mathcal{A}}. \quad (4an)$$

One may notice that (3a) is identical to (4a). The process can be repeated for all players proving eventually that models *Equil-MPES* and *Opt-MPES* are equivalent.

III. REVENUE ADEQUACY

We prove that model *Equil-MPES* is revenue-adequate. To this purpose, at the optimal solution, we multiply each expression within the physical storage rights equalities (1ga)-(1gc)

by $\mu_{s,t}^c$, $\mu_{s,t}^d$, and $\mu_{s,t}^e$, respectively. Similarly, all expressions within the power flow equality (1gd) are multiplied by λ_t^{loc} , at the optimal solution. Afterwards, we sum all the obtained equalities, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_s \left(p_{s,t}^{c,\text{ri}*} \mu_{s,t}^{c*} + p_{s,t}^{d,\text{ri}*} \mu_{s,t}^{d*} + e_{s,t}^{\text{ri}*} \mu_{s,t}^{e*} \right) + p_t^{\text{flow}*} \lambda_t^{\text{loc}*} = \\ & \sum_{i \in \hat{\mathcal{I}}, s} \left(p_{i,s,t}^{c,\max*} \mu_{s,t}^{c*} + p_{i,s,t}^{d,\max*} \mu_{s,t}^{d*} + e_{i,s,t}^{\max*} \mu_{s,t}^{e*} \right) + \\ & \sum_{i \in \hat{\mathcal{A}}, s} \left[(p_{i,s,t}^{d*} - p_{i,s,t}^{c*}) \lambda_t^{\text{loc}*} \right] + \sum_{s \in \hat{\mathcal{A}}} \left[(p_{s,t}^{d*} - p_{s,t}^{c*}) \lambda_t^{\text{loc}*} \right] + \\ & \sum_{i \in \hat{\mathcal{P}}} \left[\left(p_{i,t}^{g*} + \sum_s p_{i,s,t}^{d*} \right) \lambda_t^{\text{loc}*} \right] + \sum_{s \in \hat{\mathcal{P}}} \left[\left(p_{s,t}^{g*} + p_{s,t}^{d*} \right) \lambda_t^{\text{loc}*} \right] \\ & + \sum_{i \in (\hat{\mathcal{C}} \cup \hat{\mathcal{R}})} q_{i,t}^* \lambda_t^{\text{loc}*} + \sum_{s \in (\hat{\mathcal{C}} \cup \hat{\mathcal{R}})} q_{s,t}^* \lambda_t^{\text{loc}*} \quad \forall t \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where superscript * stands for the optimal values.

According to (5), the total payment of the players for their obtained physical storage rights and the their purchased energy to the market operator, i.e., the right-hand side, equals to the total payment of the market operator to the physical storage rights suppliers and to the grid owner. Therefore, the market operator never incurs a financial deficit, i.e., the market is revenue-adequate. Similarly, we can prove the revenue-adequacy for *Opt-MPES*.

IV. PARAMETERS AND TECHNICAL DATA FOR THE CASE STUDIES

We provide here the technical data and the parameter values used in the case studies of the main paper. Table I provides the storage (dis)charge efficiencies, the nominal (dis)charge and capacity rates, the value of lost load, as well as the remaining parameters used in the case studies.

TABLE I
PARAMETER VALUES

Parameter	Value
Charge efficiency storage type 1 η_s^c	0.81
Discharge efficiency storage type 1 η_s^d	0.85
Charge efficiency storage type 2 η_s^c	0.91
Discharge efficiency storage type 2 η_s^d	0.95
Nominal dis(charge) rate (same for type 1 and 2) $P_s^{c,\max}, P_s^{d,\max}$ [kW]	10
Nominal capacity (same for type 1 and 2) E_s^{\max} [kWh]	20
Grid line capacity L [kW]	24
Value of lost load V_i [\$/kWh]	4
Value of storage residual energy $\tilde{\lambda}$ [\$/kWh]	0.29
Offer price for dis(charge) right stor. type 1 W_s^c, W_s^d [\$/kW]	0.005
Offer price for capacity right stor. type 1 W_s^c [\$/kWh]	0.0025
Offer price for dis(charge) right stor. type 2 W_s^c, W_s^d [\$/kW]	0.01
Offer price for capacity right stor. type 2 W_s^c [\$/kWh]	0.005

Fig. 1 depicts the DA forecasts for wind and PV power production, as well as for the distribution-level DA energy price λ_t^{DA} for the next 24 hours.

Fig. 1. DA forecasts for wind-PV power production and energy price